

THE ECONOMIC AND ENVIRONMENTAL ASSESSMENT OF CASTOR OIL SUPPLY CHAIN

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ABSTRACT: Among the species cultivated for industrial vegetable oil production, castor could be a good crop for future investments due to the good resistance to pests, tolerance to drought, and suitability for marginal lands cultivation. The paper presents results of the environmental impact assessment and economic feasibility of the production of castor oil from two different castor hybrids comparing four by-products management scenarios and two harvesting systems. Castor hybrid C-856 harvested manually and that involved only the soil incorporation of press cake obtained by the oil extraction resulted as the most sustainable. The hybrid C-1030 resulted as more profitable than C-856 when harvested with the combine harvester. The ratio between gross margin and GWP emissions was applied to calculate the economic performance (gross margin) per unit of environmental burden. Findings showed that Sc1B scenario in case of C-856 cultivar hybrid had a better ratio between economic performance and greenhouse gas (GHG) emitted into the atmosphere (€3.75 per kg CO₂eq).

Keywords: bioeconomy; LCA; economic assessment; *Ricinus communis*, L.; castor oil; by-product; residue management.

1 INTRODUCTION

The world's population is estimated to exceed 9 billion people by 2050 according to FAO (2009). Thus, increasing in food and energy demand worldwide cannot be avoided: projections show that the overall food production is expected to rise by 70% [1] while the global demand for energy will increase by more than a quarter to 2040 [2]. Bioenergy production primarily aims at the greenhouse gas (GHG) reduction and achieving such a goal may lead to indirect land use change. Competition for land use among food and non-food crops is a serious issue that European Commission has been addressing for decades, and more stringent policy measures regarding sustainable production of food and energy are on the Agenda. On 1 January 2021 the proposed new directive RED II will enter into force, setting the new thresholds for minimum renewable energy share [3]. Biodiesel production from vegetable oils is feasible and widely accepted as an alternative strategy to meet these goals: It has similar properties to oil-derived diesel and, furthermore, it produces lower sulfur emission. Among the species currently cultivated for industrial vegetable oil production, castor could be a good candidate for future investments due to the good resistance to pests, tolerance to drought, and suitability for marginal lands cultivation [4]. According to FAO, in 2017, almost 1.8 million tons of castor seed had been produced worldwide, and Europe is the main user [5]. Furthermore, according to industry executives, the worldwide castor oil market is growing. In addition, the production of castor oil from *Ricinus* generates a large quantity of press cakes, husks, and crop residues [6] that, in a framework of bioeconomy, could be used as by-products for different purposes. In this framework, the European Project MAGIC (Marginal lands for Growing Industrial Crops—Grant Agreement number: 727698-MAGIC-H2020-RUR-2016-2017/H2020-RUR-2016-2) aims towards the development of resource-efficient and economically profitable industrial crops to be grown on marginal land. Among industrial crops considered in the

Project, there is *Ricinus communis*, L. (castor) that is cultivated for its seed oil, which is employed extensively in medicine, pharmaceuticals, and biorefineries [7]. To our knowledge, limited studies have been dedicated to the environmental and economic sustainability of castor [8,9]. Some studies are focused on the sustainability assessment of the residue biomass utilization [10] or biodiesel production [11] without investigating in detail the impact of the various castor agricultural stages and different residue management. In particular, a comparison of the environmental sustainability between different castor hybrids, harvesting methods, and by-products management have not been presented in the literature. Using a case study approach [12,13], the work aimed to present results concerning the estimation of the environmental impacts and economic assessment of two different castor hybrids harvested both manually and mechanically (manual vs. mechanical harvestings). Various scenarios of on-farm by-products managements were analyzed and the study carried out an economic and environmental assessment to identify the most advantageous scenario for each castor variety and residue management.

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

The study area is located in Geaca Municipality, Cluj District (Romania). Cluj District lies in the northwestern half of the country, between parallels 47°28' in North and 46°24' in South, meridians 23°39' in west and 24°13' in east, respectively. It is located in the contact zone of three representative natural units: Apuseni Mountains, Someș, Plateau, and Transylvanian Plain. Cluj District is the 12th largest in the country and accounts for almost 3% of Romania's area. It is bordered to the northeast by Maramures, and Bistrit,a-Năsăud counties, to the east by Mures, District, to the south by Alba District, and to the west by Bihor and Sălaj counties. The trials were carried out on the 8th and 9th of October 2019 in two different experimental fields where castor was harvested.

The main data of two dwarf hybrids of *Ricinus communis* (C-856 and C-1030) collected. Plants were cultivated in Romania, and seeds were provided to local farmer (Ecoricinus—National association of *Ricinus* growers) by the Israeli company KAIIMA.

The dwarf hybrids tested were two of the various chosen by the association Ecoricinus to evaluate their behavior and productivity in Romania. Although hybrid C-856 has already been analyzed in productive and morphological terms by Alexopoulou et al. [5] in Greece and Italy, hybrid C-1030 has never been described in the literature and in the present study, it has been analyzed only to assess its productivity and the amount of epigeal biomass available for the environmental and economic assessment. On the basis of farmer’s survey, two scenarios for each castor variety with a different mix of by-products management were considered (Table I).

Table I. Scenarios analyzed in the study for each castor variety (Sc1 = scenario 1; Sc2 = scenario 2)

Harvesting Systems	Manual Harvesting		Mechanical Harvesting	
	Sc1A	Sc1B	Sc2A	Sc2B
Straw	Soil incorporation	Sale	Soil incorporation	Sale
Husk	Sale	Sale	Soil incorporation	Soil incorporation
Press cake	Soil incorporation	Soil incorporation	Soil incorporation	Soil incorporation
Castor oil	Sale	Sale	Sale	Sale

Source: Our elaboration.

Pre-harvest tests were conducted directly in the field. An environmental impact analysis of castor oil production was carried out using the life cycle assessment methodology (LCA) according to UNI EN ISO 14040: 2006 [14] and UNI EN ISO 14044: 2006 [15], by means an attributional approach [16–19]. In particular, the environmental impact of 1 Mg of castor oil was based on GHG emissions. The carbon footprint was defined as the sum of all GHGs emitted within the system boundary and expressed in CO₂ eq. applying the IPCC 2007 method (100-year life span). The considered system is defined by all the agricultural processes that occurred during the *Ricinus communis* growing phase and subsequent oil extraction phase carried out at farm level (Figure 1).

In addition, the Gross margin was calculated [21] to assess the economic performances of the farm. Finally, the ratio between gross margin and GWP emissions was applied to calculate the economic performance (gross margin) per unit of environmental burden [20].

Figure 1. System boundaries

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The impact analysis allowed for identifying the processes that had higher impacts on the environment. What emerged from the analysis was that fertilization was the agricultural phase with the most impact. This result is common to various studies [22–28]. In the present study, for all cultivar hybrids and scenarios, the environmental impacts of fertilization phase were due to emissions of methane (CH₄), dinitrogen monoxide (N₂O), and carbon dioxide (CO₂) from manure management and its incorporation into the soil. In fact, fertilization emitted 74 to 89% of the GHG of the castor oil production. The LCA study of biodiesel production from rapeseed published by Malça et al. [29] reported that the cultivation stage impacted 66 to 79% and fertilization was the main cause of GHG emissions [29]. According to our results, the higher GHG emissions were mainly due to the characteristics, and the direct and indirect emissions were generated by manure itself. It should be highlighted that, as suggested by Aguilera et al. [30], organic fertilizers applied at similar N rates to synthetic fertilizers generally make smaller contributions to the leached NO₃ pool, and can mitigate N₂O emissions [30]. The different by-product management also influenced the indirect emissions of GHG due to their degradations during soil incorporation. In the case of castor oil produced by both C-856 and C-1030 cultivar hybrids, as expected, the manual harvesting resulted as more sustainable (Sc1A and Sc1B), and Sc1B scenario was always the least impactful, followed by scenarios 1A and 2B (Figures 2 and 3).

Figure 2. Carbon footprint of 1 Mg of castor oil hybrid C-856 for each scenario ((Sc1 = scenario 1; Sc2 = scenario 2).

Figure 3. Carbon footprint of 1 Mg of castor oil hybrid C-1030 for each scenario (Sc1 = scenario 1; Sc2 = scenario 2).

Moreover, among cultivar hybrids and all scenarios, Sc2A_C-1030 is more impactful than the other treatments analyzed, while the Sc1B_C-856 is less burdensome than others. These results were due to both different combinations of on-farm by-products (castor press cake incorporation into the soil in case of 1B_C-856, and castor press cake, straw and husks incorporation into the soil in case of 2A_C-1030) and yields (2.8 Mg per ha in case of C-856 vs. 2.9 Mg per ha in case of C-1030). In general, the incorporation of by-products in the soil at farm level has resulted in higher GHG emissions than their sale. For this reason, the highest impact observed in the mechanized harvesting treatments (Sc2A and Sc2B) is largely due to the non-collection of husks that are left in the field by the combine and then buried. The life cycle of scenario 1B, in which manual harvesting was assumed (less burdensome in the case of hybrid C-856, slightly less productive, and with less press cake), and with the incorporation of the pressed cake alone and the sale of the other by-products, resulted in the emission of 8.14 Mg CO₂eq per Mg of castor oil (8.14 kg CO₂eq per kg of castor oil extracted). On the other hand, the life cycle of scenario 2A_C-1030, in which mechanized harvesting with combine harvesters and the incorporation of straw, husks, and press cakes was assumed, resulted in the emission of 18.9 Mg CO₂eq per Mg of castor oil produced (18.9 kg CO₂eq per kg of castor oil extracted). Although, in Sc1A and Sc1B scenarios, there is the dehulling phase that there is not in Sc2A and Sc2B, this has a very small impact always <8% (on average 0.698 Mg CO₂eq Mg⁻¹ of castor oil produced) of the total CO₂ emissions. The oil extraction impacted less than 5% of the total CO₂ emitted (on average 0.412 Mg CO₂eq Mg⁻¹ of castor oil). Sanz Requena [26] reported that for each ton of crude sunflower, rapeseed, and soybean oil extracted, an average of 2.2 Mg of CO₂ was emitted, but it should be highlighted that after the mechanical

extraction, a treatment with a solvent (hexane) was included [26]. Spinelli [31] reported a total emission of 13.7 Mg CO₂eq Mg⁻¹ of sunflower oil produced [31]. However, according to the study and the allocation used, the emissions became 4.52 Mg CO₂eq Mg⁻¹ of sunflower oil and 9.18 Mg CO₂eq Mg⁻¹ of sunflower cake produced. The lack of allocation of a higher share of emissions from the press cake makes castor oil production inevitably more impactful in GHG emitted than other vegetable oils, although the variety C-856 with manual harvesting have relatively low and promising overall emissions.

In addition, the ratio between gross margin and GWP emissions was applied to calculate the economic performance (gross margin) per unit of environmental burden (Table II). The ratio is based on data from both environmental and economic accounting systems. The higher the ratio value, the higher the economic performance per unit of GWP emitted.

Table II. Gross margin and carbon footprint for each scenario, expressed in euro/FU (1 Mg of castor oil)-(Sc1 = scenario 1; Sc2 = scenario 2).

Cultivar Hybrid: C-856 Scenarios				
	SC1A (Man.)	SC1B (Mec.)	SC2A (Man.)	SC2B (Mec.)
Gross Margin (euro/FU)	30,533	30,537	30,671	30,675
GWP (kg CO ₂ eq/FU)	9070	8140	18,100	15,800
Gross Margin/GWP ratio	3.37	3.75	1.69	1.94

Cultivar Hybrid: C-1030 Scenarios				
	SC1A (Man.)	SC1B (Mec.)	SC2A (Man.)	SC2B (Mec.)
Gross Margin (euro/FU)	30,564	30,572	30,688	30,695
GWP (kg CO ₂ eq/FU)	14,600	11,600	18,900	16,300
Gross Margin/GWP ratio	2.09	2.63	1.62	1.88

Source: Our elaboration on both budget data (year 2018) and environmental findings.

Findings showed that scenario 1B in the case of C-856 cultivar hybrid had a better ratio between economic performance and GHG emitted into the atmosphere (euro 3.75 per kg CO₂eq); while the 2A_C-1030 scenario showed the worst ratio between economic and environmental performances (euro 1.62 per kg CO₂-eq) confirming the environmental results. These results were due to different combinations of on-farm by-products, different revenues and yields.

4 CONCLUSION

There has been a critical increment in interest for sustainable and biodegradable items so as to diminish reliance on petrochemicals. This is one of the essential elements which is driving the growth of the worldwide castor oil market. The research focused on the evaluation of the environmental and economic sustainability of two

different castor hybrids (C-856 and C-1030) comparing manual and mechanical harvesting methods, and by-product management. Comparing all the proposed scenarios, the cultivation of the manually harvested castor hybrid C-856 and the by-product management that involved only the soil incorporation of press cake obtained by the oil extraction resulted as the most sustainable. On the other hand, the mechanized harvesting of hybrid C-1030, which involved the incorporation of all the by-products of the cultivation of castor and production of castor oil (husk, straw, and press cake) showed the highest CO₂ emissions per Mg of castor oil (+132%). It is therefore clear how, with the same inputs used, the castor-oil cultivation method affects the management of by-products and how, while residues are a source of organic matter for the soil, they cause greenhouse gas emissions during the degradation process in the soil. In the end, to determine the most economically and environmentally convenient scenario, the ratio between gross margin and GWP emissions was applied to calculate the economic performance (gross margin) per unit of environmental burden. Findings showed that scenario Sc1B in the case of C-856 cultivar hybrid had a better ratio between economic performance and GHG emitted into the atmosphere (euro3.75 per kg CO₂eq); while the Sc2A_C-1030 scenario showed the worst ratio between economic and environmental performances (euro1.62 per kg CO₂eq) confirming the environmental results. Although Sc1B represents a good economic–environmental compromise, including manual harvesting, it clashes both with the need to innovate the castor production chain, and with the costs and availability of labor that may vary over time, affecting the sustainability of the chain, costs, and market prices. Furthermore, an important aspect that was not considered in the study is the loss of product during harvesting. This is particularly relevant in the case of very high losses that are reflected in the impacts per unit of product. With the implementation of well-functioning mechanized castor harvesting systems, the resulting seed losses will also necessarily have to be considered in future studies. Moreover, it is important to highlight that the study did not consider the whole process downstream of the castor oil extraction and the related impacts that could completely reverse the results obtained, which should be investigated in future researches.

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8 LOGO SPACE

